

A STUDY ON STUDENT'S PERCEPTION REGARDING MOBILE-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING AT THE UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL AT SHAHEED BENAZIR BHUTTO UNIVERSITY SANGHAR CAMPUS

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Abstract

The aim of the research is to investigate students' perception regarding mobile assisted language learning in improving students' language skills at undergraduate level. Despite the growing use of mobile devices in education, students' perceptions of mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) remain unexplored at the undergraduate level in rural Pakistani contexts. Understanding their attitudes is vital for effective language instruction. Therefore, this study used qualitative method and semi structured interviews were conducted from 8 participants of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Sanghar Campus, selected by purposive sampling. Thematic analysis was adopted to interpret the transcribed data. Findings of this study revealed that students use their mobile phones for English language learning and interactions on social media and shows positive attitude towards using mobile phone applications to learn English, as reported conclude this study suggest that it's important to recognize the benefits of using mobile technology in education. Future research investigates the opinions of a larger pool of participants for a more understanding

INTRODUCTION

Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) and patterns of MALL play a pivotal role as factors influencing language acquisition in the present era. According to Zohaib et al. (2025) one of the most effective methods for teaching and learning the English language is mobile technology, often known as mobile assisted language learning, or MALL. In higher education, improving one's ability to speak English is still crucial, particularly in non-native settings like Pakistan where students frequently don't have enough opportunity to communicate in real life (Mughal & Shah, 2025). According to research, student opinions about MALL are crucial to its effective use since they effect participation and

academic results (Abbasi & Ali, 2024). With its portable and adaptable learning resources, Mobile-Assisted Language Acquisition (MALL) has become a game-changing method in higher education, especially when it comes to improving language acquisition (Shaheen, 2023). A move toward more independent and technologically driven teaching methods is evident in the growing dependence of technologically driven teaching methods is evident in the growing dependence of undergraduate students on mobile applications for language acquisition (Sharipov et al., 2024).

This study aims to investigate students' perceptions regarding MALL and their engagement with device,

assessing their potential impact on acquiring second languages, particularly focusing on English resources to enhance their language proficiency. In this initial chapter, the groundwork for the research is laid out. The context of the study underscores the imperative for conducting this research and highlights the interplay between technological advancements and the acquisition of second languages.

In contemporary time, global economic interaction have transcended geographical boundaries, with the surge of professional online sales systems amplifying the significance and boundaries, with the surge of professional online sales systems amplifying the significance and necessity of mastering the English language. Beyond economic considerations, social forces exert substantial influence on language acquisition. While previous eras allowed for localized interactions, the modern world operates in a highly interconnected manner, rendering individuals susceptible to rapid global shifts. The pervasive impact of trends is evident through mediums like cinema, television series, and social media applications, which hold sway on a worldwide scale.

These technological conduits are conveniently accessible through mobile phones, thereby fostering a desire among individuals to engage in cross-cultural conversations using English. These underlying factors have remained relevant until the 20th century.

The amalgamation of media and technology commenced during the 1950s when small language centers began integrating movies and tape recorders as tools to enhance English instruction's efficacy. The subsequent decades witnessed the development of audio and video courses through multimedia projectors and slide shows in the '70s and '80s. By the mid-'90s, the Internet facilitated the availability of numerous multimedia language programs for educators (Ahmad, 2012). The 20th and 21st centuries have witnessed a transformation in language learning, not only in terms of motivations but also in the methods employed. The pivotal catalyst for this transformation is undoubtedly the ubiquity of media, facilitated by its accessibility on mobile phones. The radio, once the solitary non-written medium, has undergone significant evolution in sync with technological advancements. Presently, media outlets encompass television, radio, social media networks,

online games, cinema, and, notably, mobile phones that encapsulate all these sources. These resources, coupled with the Internet, assume diverse roles in enhancing learners' foreign language comprehension and production, granting them the flexibility to access information at their convenience, irrespective of time and location. Consider the case of social media applications like Instagram, which, despite their finite functionalities, can prove advantageous within language classrooms due to the contextualized visual content they offer. This visual aid particularly benefits visual learners (Al-Ali, 2014). Similarly, Kennedy's study in 2018 highlighted how learners perceive mobile phones as personalized assistants, enabling them to make informed choices regarding applications tailored to their language learning requirements within foreign language education.

The Internet's emergence as a contemporary teaching tool, particularly for enhancing vocabulary knowledge, has led to advancements in foreign language learning. Activities centered around gaming have also demonstrated affirmative links with lexical learning performance (Chen et al., 2019). This digital landscape, characterized by computers and the Internet, transcends the realm of lexical items and grammar rules, encapsulating the broader nuances of language acquisition (Monica - Ariana, Anamaria - Mirabela, 2014).¹¹ In the modern era, the integration of mobile media sources into daily activities is nearly universal. However, research on the actual application of these sources to support teaching and learning remains insufficient. Limited explanations exist regarding how mobile computing tools and social media are harnessed by college students (Gikas & Grant, 2013). Given the ubiquity of English across various genres, exposure to an extensive English vocabulary through media texts is commonplace. The convergence of computing power, portability, wireless communication, and contextual sensitivity positions one-to-one computing as a potent learning tool within both conventional classrooms and informal learning environments (Sung, Chang & Liu, 2016).

Frequent users of mobile media tools are expected to incorporate the acquired input into their verbal expressions. Exposure to TV news and radio programs equips students with knowledge, structures, strategies,

and vocabulary applicable to everyday scenarios (CaoBahrani, 2011). Students who embrace novelty and are willing to explore new tools and applications are exposed to diverse media content with just a few taps on their mobile devices. Despite this, limited studies have endeavored to capture learners' perspectives regarding the use of such applications to bolster foreign language learning. Thus, the objective of this study is to uncover the extent to which students leverage media for enhancing their foreign language learning journey.

Despite the growing use of mobile devices in education, students' perceptions of mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) remain unexplored at the undergraduate level in rural Pakistani contexts. Understanding their attitudes is vital for effective language instruction (Khan & Raza, 2024). This study investigates students' perceptions of MALL at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Sanghar Campus.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the students' perception regarding mobile assisted language learning at undergraduate level at shaheed Benazir Bhutto university Sanghar campus?
2. What is the effectiveness of mobile-assisted language learning in improving undergraduate students' language skills?

Numerous studies have explored the intersection of technology and language learning. Yet, Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) represents a contemporary approach, coinciding with the rapid evolution of student learning habits. Educators are confronted with the need to not only acknowledge but also leverage mobile phones as tools for language learning, both within and beyond the classroom. In response, this study aims to uncover and analyze university students' perceptions and attitudes towards MALL. Specifically, the investigation centers on its application within their English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses, shedding light on the potential benefits and challenges associated with integrating mobile technology into foreign language education. Through this exploration, the study endeavors to offer insights that can inform effective teaching practices and

contribute to the broader discourse on contemporary language education methodologies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section aims to present previous research to shed light on interconnected domains, including the integration of technology in acquiring foreign languages and the theoretical foundations of the contemporary language learning environment. The exploration commences with broader facets of language acquisition, investigating the significance of the English language and its prevalent impact in media channels. Furthermore, an in-depth examination of learning methodologies and the accessibility of technology-driven learning resources is referenced.

TECHNOLOGY AND LANGUAGE LEARNING

The integration of education and technology has experienced rapid progress in recent decades. This development arises from the fact that English educators have largely maintained their traditional method and attitudes, while technological advancements have played a pivotal role. Within the realm of education, audio resources and technological tools have become commonplace. Prominent book publishers now incorporate online teaching aids, digital workbooks, auditory materials, and visual assets into their educational packages. The proficient application of these resources has significantly elevated the quality of language instruction and learning experiences.

Various educational programs have been devised, including Computer-Assisted Instruction (CIA), Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), and Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL). These initiatives require learners to possess specific skills in order to actively engage in the learning process. The utilization of technology for learning presents both advantages and disadvantages. On the positive side, it offers personalized learning, enabling students to study according to their individual proficiency levels. It also caters to individualized needs, and furthermore, computer assisted learning contributes to the reduction of external distractions. Shish (2017), underscores the significance of incorporating technological tools within the classroom. The

dynamic classroom environment, coupled with the integration of mobile technologies, has facilitated flexible and convenient language acquisition for both students and educators. The dynamic classroom environment, coupled with the integration of mobile technologies, has facilitated flexible and convenient language acquisition for both students and educators. To effectively address the intensive demands of the learning process, staying up-to-date with evolving technology is imperative. This perspective maintains that while the ever-changing technological landscape poses challenges for language instructors and learners, meeting these challenges ensures their success in attaining a more productive future in the era of mobile technology (Shih, 2017).

COMPUTER-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING (CALL)

During the 20th century, technology made its way into various aspects of daily life, including education. This integration of technology has significantly impacted the global teaching and learning of foreign languages, leading to the adoption of diverse methodologies. One of the most transformative teaching methods, bringing about changes in role and responsibilities, is the incorporation of computers. Capitalizing on the advantages offered by computers, an instructional system known as Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CAAL) has been established. The availability of personal computers and the enthusiasm of educators eager to embrace technological advancements have driven the integration of computers both with and beyond classroom setting. Numerous scholars have provided their distinct definitions of CALL, reflecting its diverse interpretations and approaches. For instance, Egbert (2005), characterizes CALL as "learners learning language in any context with, through, and around computer technologies." Similarly, Levy (1997), defines CALL as "the search for and study of applications of the computer in language teaching and learning." In another perspective, Beatty (2003), identifies CALL as "any process in which a learner uses a computer and, as a result, improves his or her language. "In the 21 context of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), computers function as tools that execute tasks assigned by humans.

Consequently, computers primarily provide an array of tasks and instructions designed by educators for language learners. These tasks encompass activities such as translation checks, grammar exercises, pronunciation practice, spelling activities, dictation exercises, close tests, sentence arrangement exercises, and more. Software programs integrated within CALL facilitate learners' engagement with computer-based activities, as articulated by Warschauer and Healey (1998), CALL offers authentic, native-speaker language models across various media formats, presents a language learning curriculum, evaluates assessments, records the learning process, and is available at any time. CALL is advantageous for fostering the development of all four language skills. It supports incidental reading and reading comprehension exercises for improving reading skills. For writing, CALL provides features such as error correction, automatic word processing, and assistance in effectively organizing text. Speaking skills, involving oral communication and the presentation of ideas, can be enhanced through simulations, role-plays, and discussions. Computer simulations serve as valuable stimuli for these activities, providing dynamic scenarios for students to engage in discussions and express their thoughts. Computers contribute significantly to the improvement of oral skills. While CALL offers advantages, it also presents challenges. The benefits primarily cater to learners, enabling them to participate actively in interactive and negotiated activities.

Learners can practice listening skills in authentic environments, exposing themselves to the target language in meaningful contexts. This approach encourages language use and provides ample time and feedback for enhancing listening abilities. Learners' autonomy is supported, as CALL allows for privacy and the flexibility to study at one's own pace. However, the disadvantages of CALL relate to learners' autonomy and technological skills. Learners need to familiarize themselves with computers and software, and computers may not be suitable for all language learning activities. CALL may not effectively address emotional and social aspects of learning, and computers cannot facilitate open-ended dialogues and conversations. Learners may benefit more from

immersion in a genuine learning environment rather than relying solely on pre-designed activities.

MOBILE-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING (MALL)

Mobile learning (m-learning) is characterized by its individualistic, spontaneous, casual, and pervasive nature. Studying with mobile phones may take longer compared to computers, but Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) offers freedom in terms of place and time (Miangah and Nezarat, 2012). Unlike Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), MALL grants learners the flexibility to engage in language learning both within and outside the classroom, facilitating learning anytime and anywhere. MALL addresses constraints associated with time and location in language learning. Mobile learning technology has rapidly evolved from a text-based teacher-learner approach to encompass future multimedia technologies. Additionally, podcast lectures and digitized audio feedback enhance communication between teachers and learners, without the limitations of time and space. Mobile learning also fosters group learning, promoting interaction among learners to share knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Collaborative learning with I an mobile learning environment encourages learners to support, inspire, and evaluate each other, leading to significant achievements. MALL encompasses a range of devices, including MP3/MP4 players, smartphones, e-book readers, laptops, and tablets. These devices serve as platforms for accessing mobile learning resources and applications, enabling engagement in language learning activities using various portable and convenient devices. The past two decades have witnessed substantial growth in the field of mobile technology, alongside extensive advancements (Burstn, 2013). The Stanford Learning Lab initiated early projects using cell phones to explore their use in language learning (Brown, 2001). Spanish language research programs have utilized cell phone voice and

email services, providing vocabulary practice, quizzes, translations, and access to live tutors. Research has shown potential for successful quiz delivery through cell phones and the utilization of automatic speech vocabulary lessons and quizzes (Thornton and Houser, 2002).

Researchers like Levy and Kennedy (2005), have developed systems using mobile technology for language learning purposes, such as sending vocabulary terms and idioms via SMS in spaced distribution formats, followed by quizzes and questions. Kiernan and Aizawa (2004), have investigated the usefulness and effectiveness of cell phones for language learning, particularly task-based learning. While mobile technologies offer advantages like simplicity, low cost, and user-friendliness, there are also challenges such as low screen size and dependency on networks. While MALL encompasses various portable devices, recent studies predominantly focus on smartphone assisted language learning.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The TAM model, originally proposed by Davis (1986), explains users' acceptance of information systems from the standpoint of the external factors' influencing the users' acceptance of a technology. Davis (1986) suggested that this model simulates the situation where users become adopters of a certain newly introduced technology. The TAM model assumes that external factors will exert influence on internal factors, perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease-of-use (PEOU), which will affect the user's attitude (A) towards using that technology. The attitude toward using technology will impact the user's behavioral intention (BI) to use or not to use the new technology. Finally behavioral intention (BI) will determine whether or not users actually use the system (Davis, 1986). The illustration of these relationships in the TAM model is shown.

METHODOLOGY

This study applied a qualitative method approach to collect data. The data was gathered in a descriptive form with respect to the scope and nature of the issue. The researcher has attempted to collect data to explore the perception of the students about mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) for that purpose the researcher has used a qualitative method of data collection. This research pursuit to explore the perception of students regarding (MALL) at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Sanghar campus. Creswell, J W & Poth, C. N. (2017). Qualitative research is a methodology used in social sciences and other fields to gain a deep understanding of human behavior, experiences, and phenomena. The qualitative approach was used because it provided insights that would assist the reader in visualizing the experiences of the people

To obtain concrete data about the use of MALL at shaheed Benazir Bhutto university, Sanghar Campus. The researcher conducted the interview with 8 students who are currently enrolled in English - (Functional English). Department. Semi-structured interviews were conducted and questions in the interview were similar to the questionnaire.

The researcher used random sampling which is commonly used method in research sampling is employed to select a group of individuals from larger population. The key characteristic of this method is that each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected (Smith, 2020).

FINDINGS

The study conducted a qualitative data analysis through a semi-structured interview with eight English studies students. The interview consisted of six main questions, with some questions supported by related sub-questions. The first question asked about the types of applications the students downloaded, and

they listed popular social media apps such as Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp, which are commonly use worldwide. The students expressed a positive attitude towards using mobile phone applications to learn English, as reported in a previous study by Miangah, T.M., & Nezarat, A. (2012). The study also revealed that students use their mobile phones for English language learning and interactions on social media. However, the interview failed to capture data on other types of apps, such as those related to hobbies or photo editing, which might have been useful to understand students' diverse interests. The second question asked the participates if they come across English content on their phones. Most students replied positively, stating that they often came across English content on social media apps. . Kiernan and Aizawa (2004) have also investigated the usefulness of cell phones for language learning. The third question was related to the second, asking if the students approved of the English content they encountered. The study found that the students were more motivated to learn English if they were interested in the genre of the content. The fourth question aimed to understand the student's motivation for learning English. The study found that the students were motivated by MALL, private communication, entertainment, and playing video games. Playing video games was found to have a positive effect on communication ability, adaptability, and resourcefulness in learners. All the students answered positively to the fifth question, which asked about their use of dictionaries while studying. Most students preferred to use dictionary applications based on the length of the content, while some relied on Google Translate for sentence-based text. The last question aimed to deduce the most crucial conclusion of the interview. The study found that most students agreed that English proficiency can be developed through Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL).

However, the study also found that MALL cannot be the sole source of learning English, and mobile phones can only be used to improve vocabulary and receptive skills, rather than productive skills. The study was conducted with English majors at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Sanghar Campus, and the data was collected through semi-structured interviews.

Q1. What are the students' perception regarding mobile assisted language learning at undergraduate level at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Sanghar Campus?

App do you regularly use on yourphone?

The responses indicate varying perspectives on mobile app usage. Some participants frequently use social media apps like Facebook and YouTube, while others believe classroom learning is more effective than learning through apps. Additionally, some respondents mention using puzzle games to improve their vocabulary. These insights highlight their opinions on the educational value of mobile application.

I regularly use Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter, Netflix, and YouTube on my mobile (see, p2, p3, p6).

There are different kinds of apps that I'm using, for example, YouTube, WhatsApp, Google Translator, Dictionary, Merriam-Webster.

Yes, I use different apps but mostly Facebook, YouTube etc.

No apps are not useful, I don't think we people learn through them but we learn more from classrooms.

Yes, I use usually puzzle game which help me to enhance my vocab.

Other apps specifically for learning

Responses reveal diverse perspective on using mobile app for learning. Some participants relay on specific educational tools like Google translator dictionary and apps such as Reallife English and lingo BlaBla for language environment. Others indicates entertainment apps like Instagram and YouTube into their learning process by engaging with English subtitles, memes and movie clips. Meanwhile some individuals use as based on necessity rather than regular practice indicating varying level of dependance on digital platform for language learning.

No, not regularly, but sometimes I use to practice my English on the app named 'RealLife English.'

It's an app where anybody can practice their English language skills. Along with this, I also use YouTube to practice my English."

Yes, there are so many apps, but I used to get help from Google and Google Dictionary, specifically for learning my English skills.

I mostly use 'Instagram' for entertainment as well as for learning English too.

I learn 'English vocab' through memes and movie clips with English subtitles.

Yes, I'm using the YouTube app for polishing my English skills. It's easy to use and free to access and very helpful for learning purposes.

Yes, I do use different apps for learning English skills, specifically 'Google Translator,' 'Dictionary Merriam-Webster,' and apart from that, there's an app named 'Learn Different Vocab' and another app that I used for English learning, 'Lingo BlaBla English.'

Basically, I'm not using apps for learning English...

No, I don't because it depends on need, so I use most of the time different apps according to my needs.

Incorporate mobile devices into your English language learning routine

The responses highlight various ways while devices are integrated into English language learning. Many participants use specialized apps to enhance vocabulary and listening skills making effective use of their time. Digital and social media platform such as Netflix and online courses also play a role in language learning by providing exposure to spoken English. Additionally recording and reviewing speech helps with pronunciation practice. The responses indicate that mobile devices serve as both a learning tool and a source of motivation for improving English proficiency.

"When I go to work every day, I use my phone to learn English with special apps. It helps me make good use of my time."

"I learn English every day using apps on my phone. I focus on getting better at words and listening."

"I learn English using my phone. I use special apps that help me."

"I easily mix my phone with learning English. I listen to English conversation Netflix series."

"I like watching English movies and shows with my

phone, and I use subtitles to help me understand better."

"Talking to people from different places and practicing English – I do this with my phone."

"I record myself talking and listen again to get better at pronouncing words."

"I take online courses and find study materials, which keeps me motivated for learning."

Use of phone as a tool for learning English, such as for vocabulary, grammar, or pronunciation practice

The responses indicate that mobile phones serve as a valuable tool for learning English by enhancing motivation, providing diverse resources and offering varied learning methods. Many participants use apps like Google translator, Oxford dictionary and Duolingo to improve vocabulary and grammar. YouTube and BBC news are commonly used for listening practice and understanding complex language rules. Some learners get with interactive methods such as vocabulary games and memes, while otherwise on WhatsApp and other platforms for informal language practice. The responses highlight the flexibility and accessibility of mobile assistant language learning.

Yes, it helps me to motivate to practice my English language skill.

Not every day, but I often use it to practice my English skill on my mobile phone, like I use games for vocab learning.

Yes, often I use my mobile phone whenever I need help. If I don't understand anything, for example, the rules of tenses, then I usually open my YouTube and get help from that, and there are other apps also that I use for practicing my English skill.

I used to get help from Google Translator as well as Oxford Dictionary, and a game that I use to practice my vocab and learn my grammar skill.

I use mostly Google Translator because it has a unique feature; whenever I use to search a word, I'll get synonyms and full usage, etc., too.

Mostly, I use WhatsApp and other platforms through which I try to practice and learn the English language. Examples from memes, etc.

I use apps for vocab and grammar; rarely do online tests for pronunciation. I watch videos and listen to BBC News.

I use to get help from my mobile, rarely.

Yes, I do use to practice my English language skill from different apps, such as Duolingo and BBC for listening purposes.

Actively pay attention to improving your English skills

The responses suggest varying levels of attentiveness towards improving English skills through mobile devices. Some learners engaged in requirement-based learning using their phones to clarify exam related queries or specific language needs. Other adopt a casual approach occasionally learning vocabulary from memes, short clips or movies. Regular learners actively incorporate English learning into their daily routine utilizing blogs, games and interactions with native speakers.

No, I don't, because I don't use my mobile especially for learning English. But sometimes when I see any interesting English video, meme, or movie clip, then I usually watch; otherwise, not.

Yeah, it's casual... because it's rare when I use my mobile only for learning English. But I learn vocab through memes and short clips.

It's 50-50 because it depends on my need. When I need to learn something, then I actively pay attention; otherwise, not.

Sometimes when I need, I use to clear my exam questions; then, of course, I fully pay my attention while using my smartphone toward learning English, as well as my subject.

Yes, on a daily basis when I use my mobile, I fully pay my attention and always try to learn new things like vocab from movies, memes, even when we play games with native speakers. I also learn a lot of things from them.

It depends on my mood; sometimes yes, I do pay attention toward learning English-relevant things while using my device, but sometimes I only use my mobile for entertainment purposes.

Yes, I do pay my attention while using my phone; I make sure to read material that helps me enhance my reading skills as well as vocab.

Yes, I do, every time I learn English vocab from blog posts.

Q2. To investigate the effectiveness of mobile-assisted language learning in improving students' language skills.

Effectiveness of Learning English by Using Mobile Applications

The responses from students indicated that mobile applications play a significant role in supporting English language learning. Participants reported that these apps are particularly effective in enhancing vocabulary and improving pronunciation. One student emphasized that mobile apps provide focused features such as pronunciation guides and vocabulary exercises, which contribute directly to speaking fluency. Others noted that learning through apps allows greater flexibility, enabling practice anytime and anywhere. Some students (S3, S5) appreciated that convenience, saying they could study while traveling or during breaks making learning more integrated into daily life. Another participant (S7) highlighted that combining mobile apps with other learning methods, such as classroom discussions or tutoring, leads to better results. However, while the general view favored app usage, a few (S8, S9) emphasized that app-based learning is most effective when used alongside structured teaching, not as a complete replacement.

IMPROVEMENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH MOBILE APPLICATIONS

According to students' responses, a noticeable improvement in various language skills was observed after they started using mobile applications. Participants highlighted that their reading comprehension had improved significantly, as mobile apps exposed them to diverse texts and interactive reading exercises. One student (S2) stated that regular reading on apps enhanced their understanding of complex sentences and vocabulary. Others reported a boost in speaking confidence, noting that speaking exercises and voice messaging features in apps helped reduce hesitation and encouraged spontaneous expression. In addition, students (S4, S6) shared that consistent listening practice through mobile audio and video content improved their ability to understand different accents and everyday conversations. Vocabulary expansion was another major area of improvement, with students (S1, S5) saying they learned new words and expressions daily, which enriched their communication skills. A few

students (S7, S10) also noted increased familiarity with idiomatic expressions and cultural references, which deepened their understanding of English usage in real-life contexts.

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MOBILE-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING APPLICATION

Students also provided several suggestions for enhancing the effectiveness of mobile-assisted language learning. One key recommendation was the inclusion of progress tracking and rewards, where students (S3, S5) expressed interest in features like badges, milestones, and updated content, noting that regular updates with relevant and interesting materials would keep learners motivated and aligned with current language trends. Another suggestion involved collaborative features, such as options for learners to interact with peers through discussion boards of live that support. Some students (S6, S8) felt that these would allow them to practice speaking and share learning tips. A few participants (S2, S4) advocated for real-life conversational scenarios, suggesting that role-plays and situational dialogues be integrated to improve practical language use. Personalized learning paths were also recommended, with students (S1, S7) proposing adaptive lesson tailored to individual proficiency levels.

Moreover, some suggested incorporating AI-powered feedback on pronunciation and grammar to help learners self-correct and improve continuously. While most students provided constructive feedback, a few (S9) felt current apps already met their needs and required no changes.

DISCUSSION

The research aimed to uncover insights into how students perceive the use of mobile devices for language learning and to assess the overall effectiveness of MALL in enhancing language skills among undergraduate students. To summarize the result concerning students' intentions to use MALL, it was evident to the majority of participants encountered minimal difficulties in navigating and utilizing MALL tools. Notably, students found MALL, particularly the apps they use and social media applications, to be user-friendly and effective as

language learning tools. This aligns with prior research, as Alexiadou and Sougari (2025) found a similar sentiment among participants, with a high agreement on the effectiveness and ease of use of technology tools like Google Classroom. The segment addressing attitudes toward MALL revealed a positive outlook among students, with the majority expressing the MALL, including social media apps, contributed significantly to their learning processes. This positive perception mirrors the finding of Gaudu (2025), suggesting that students recognize and appreciate the benefits offered by mobile-assisted language learning. Expand study to other private universities to enhance diversity and quality.

Include students with diverse backgrounds for a more comprehensive perspective.

Compare views of students at private and public universities to identify similarities and differences.

Investigate the opinions of a larger pool of participants for a more robust understanding.

Gain insights into university students' feelings about mobile device use for language learning through broader research approaches.

CONCLUSION

This research looked at what students think about using mobile phones for language learning. It involved 8 students studying English for Specific Purposes from shaheed Benazir Bhutto university sanghar campus departments of English studies. The results showed that most students agree that using mobile phones is helpful for learning languages. They are especially interested in using mobile apps for learning English, and they pay more attention when the content is in English. Surprisingly, the students' field of study didn't make a big difference, but gender did. Female students are more interested in using mobile phones for language learning than male students. These findings suggest that it's important to recognize the benefits of using mobile technology in education. Both inside and outside the classroom, we need to adapt to the needs of modern education. The study also found that students are more engaged in language learning when they find the topic or content interesting, according to the qualitative data.

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